

SECTION OF CHEMICAL SCIENCES

WEATHER - RESISTANT PAINT COATINGS FOR CORROSION PROTECTION OF METAL STRUCTURES TECHNOLOGICAL EQUIPMENT

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Abstract

Due to the ever-increasing rates in all industries, the number of metal structures and equipment operated in aggressive environments is increasing. The study of the durability of oil and gas industry equipment exposed to aggressive environments is one of the main tasks. To increase the durability of machine parts in mechanical engineering and the oil and gas industry, it is necessary to take measures that reduce or exclude aggressive effects on equipment and structures. The required durability of machine parts, various metal structures and equipment in the presence of aggressive influences can be ensured by the use of various protective coatings, which are divided into the main types: paint, thick-layer or mastic, film and facing. Paint coatings have the ability to form a solid, thin film on the protected surface with certain physico-chemical and physico-mechanical properties. The use of paint coatings in the protection of metal structures and equipment is determined by a number of features. The main ones are: the predominant need for the use of paint and varnish materials, for which the cold curing mode is sufficient, due to the need for periodic renewal in operating conditions; economic feasibility of using low-layer coatings with a long service life; high demand for chemically resistant durable coatings. The use of paint coatings and their cost-effectiveness is explained by the possibilities of manufacturing paint materials of various formulations that provide the required properties in the coating. In industry, cold-drying paint and varnish materials are most often used. Coatings based on epoxy resins are thermosetting materials after curing and have acquired optimal strength properties after heat treatment at 180-200°C for 10-20 hours. Polymer materials are widely used in modern technology, which have a number of advantages over traditional materials - metals. However, in some cases, it is necessary to preserve the advantages inherent in metals, in particular, electrical conductivity, while polymer materials in the vast majority of cases are dielectrics.

Keywords: aggressive environment, corrosion resistance, coatings, protection, gossypol resin.

In the fuel and energy complex of the Republic of Kazakhstan, an important place is occupied by the pipeline transportation system of energy sources, for which the machine-building industry manufactures equipment for the extraction, preparation and transportation of energy sources to the ultimate customer. The specificity of this equipment is to work in various aggressive environments, so great importance is attached to the development of methods to protect it from corrosion. Corrosion failures lead to colossal material costs for the repair and replacement of equipment, and a separate point of indirect increase in costs is the idle time of equipment caused by its failure and emergency fillings of extracted and transported products. The most urgent task

is corrosion protection of the internal surface of equipment, including oil pipelines in contact with aggressive environments [1]. In this regard now there is a growing need for anti-corrosion coatings used for various production needs, which gave a new round of development of the industry to create new and improve existing anti-corrosion coatings. The largest volume of metal intensity in oilfield equipment is occupied by pipes of various purposes and assortments, therefore, in research work the object of research is anti-corrosion polymer coatings of oil pipeline pipes, the most common and effective for protecting oilfield pipes from corrosion. To date, there is a wide selection of anti-corrosion polymer coatings with different performance properties and

characteristics, which makes it much more difficult to choose. To make an objective choice of polymer coatings for specific operating conditions, it is necessary to conduct their high-quality laboratory tests, but there is a problem of quality control of the materials used and finished coatings. In the fuel and energy complex of the Republic of Kazakhstan, an important place is occupied by the pipeline transportation system of energy sources, which is characterized by a significant length (more than 230 thousand km), the safety of operation of which largely depends on the quality of their corrosion protection. In particular, one of the most important methods of preventing corrosion of equipment, including oil and gas pipelines in contact with aggressive environments is the protection of the inner surface with insulating coatings. The factors that cause the aggressiveness of water to the corrosive material include the salts contained in it, pH, water hardness as well as the content of acid gases. For example, salts dissolved in water are electrolytes, an increase in the concentration of which increases the electrical conductivity of the medium and as a result accelerates corrosion. Currently, the production of oil wells is characterized by a high degree of water cutting, the presence of carbon dioxide and hydrogen sulfide dissolved in water, as well as the presence of corrosive microorganisms. One of the most effective methods against inner corrosion of the pipelines to apply various coatings to their inner surface.

The most common coatings are polymer-based (epoxy, novolac, polyurethane), to a lesser extent silicate-enamel coatings (mainly to protect the inner surface of the tubing), cement-sand (to protect fishing pipes). Anti-corrosion coatings prevent contact of metal with the transported fluid. Anti-corrosion coatings have a number of undoubted advantages which are deprived of other methods of protection: reducing the roughness of the inner surface of the pipe and as a result reducing hydraulic resistance and increasing the productivity of the pipeline; reduction of the amount of asphalt-milk paraffin deposits; reduction of operating costs, compared to inhibitory protection. At the present the first place among the methods of corrosion protection of the internal surface of oil pipelines is occupied by coatings on an organic basis. With the help of these synthetic materials effective quick-drying coatings are obtained. Organic-based coatings combine the optimal properties necessary for protection since they can significantly increase the service life and have a low cost. A significant part of high-molecular compounds are polymers on an organic basis. The protective properties of the paint coating are due to the mechanical and chemical properties of the film, as well as the adhesion to the substrate material. According to the technology of coating on an organic basis they are divided into liquid and powder. The traditional type of paint and varnish products are liquid paints - solutions and dispersions - liquid bodies, which contain polymers obtained by polymerization methods in solutions and in dispersed systems and organic solvents. The use of organosoluble formulations is due to the fact that the vast majority of film-forming agents dissolve in organic solvents and not in water. Paint and varnish compositions

are divided depending on the solvent content into materials with low dry residue (film formers - polymers, oligomers and their mixtures) and with a high dry residue. Pipes with an internal polymer coating have not only high corrosion resistance, but also increased smoothness which in turn reduces the deposition of paraffin on the walls of the pipes and thereby increases the speed of passage of products. Their high resistance to moisture as well as to various salts is noted. Polymer-coated pipes are wear-resistant and have a high service life of 20 years. The criteria for choosing internal anti-corrosion coatings for pipeline networks are operating conditions, protective and technological properties of coatings. The most suitable coatings that meet certain conditions in the petroleum industry are polymeric, among which the most famous are epoxy and polyurethane. Epoxy resins are low-molecular polymers (oligomers or monomers) that can pass from a thermoplastic state to thermoset (cured) state under the influence of chemically interacting substances (hardeners) with them. Epoxy coatings as anti-corrosion film formers have a number of advantages. On the one hand, these include operational characteristics. Epoxy coatings for pipelines have increased heat resistance, although the basic temperature in the operating conditions of a linear pipeline is 60 ° C. In addition, they can be stored for a long time in the open air. On the other hand, they include technological characteristics. Curability of coatings occurs both at room temperature and at low temperature conditions (in the presence of catalysts). Epoxy-based coatings are highly resistant to aggressive environments, to abrasive wear, while maintaining high mechanical properties. A number of advantages of epoxy coatings characterize their resistance to corrosion processes. Coatings on an epoxy basis are resistant to cathode flaking, which is associated with the absence of stress - corrosion. Protective anticorrosion coatings based on epoxy resins have high barrier properties. In addition, epoxy resins are dielectrics, which contributes to the electrical insulation of oil pipelines. Another important advantage of epoxy coatings is good adhesion to various materials. There are many methods for assessing the quality of anti-corrosion polymer coatings. The initial assessment of the properties of anti-corrosion polymer coatings in most cases is associated with the analysis of appearance. Visual inspection when compared with the standard allows you to identify obvious types of defects, and special measuring instruments help to determine the destruction at the micro level. Analysis of the appearance of coatings allows you to evaluate other properties of the coating. For example, a coating that is short will have a more saturated gloss, whereas otherwise the gloss coefficient decreases. Elasticity characterizes the resistance of the coating to deformation loads. One of the key parameters characterizing anti-corrosion polymer coatings is the thickness of the dry coating film, since at a low coating thickness its corrosive properties decrease, and at high - mechanical (in particular, impact strength) [2]. Impact resistance capability characterizes the mechanical strength of the coating and its ability to withstand mechanical stress during the installation, storage and

operation of pipe water. The adhesive strength of coatings is almost crucial for establishing the suitability of a material as an anti-corrosion polymer coating. The degree of adhesion determines the strength of chemical bonds, as well as their direct amount, and therefore, the degree of purity and uniformity of the surface are of decisive importance. The wear resistance of coatings is determined by their ability to withstand periodic and/or constant destructive effects as a result of contact with other bodies and media. In accordance with the mechanism there are destruction, adhesive, fatigue, abrasive and erosive wear. One of the indicators on the basis of which it is possible to predict the service life of anti-corrosion coatings is the water absorption coefficient - the higher it is the more moisture the coating can absorb, which in turn leads to the destruction of cohesive and adhesive bonds. In real conditions, anti-corrosion polymer coatings are operated under the influence of various media at elevated pressures and temperatures, and therefore there is a need for laboratory tests that simulate operating conditions. The problem of corrosion protection is very urgent. The most universal effective and affordable way to protect metal products from corrosion is the application of paint and varnish materials. About 80% of all metal surfaces are protected by paints. However, the durability and effectiveness of paint protection is largely determined by the quality of surface preparation before painting. The durability of structures and equipment operated in conditions of production with aggressive environments depend on the use of various anti-corrosion coatings. Currently, various paint and varnish materials are used to protect various structures and equipment from corrosion. Epoxy coatings, paints, rust converters, putty compounds, etc. are particularly widespread. The theoretical basis of such developments is the fundamental research of the processes of corrosion and mechanical damage. The detailed study of the mechanisms of formation of protective films formed on the basis of chemical interaction with the surface layer of the metal itself makes it possible to develop optimal formulations based on acceptable components and as the main fillers of local waste. The basic branches of the industry play a decisive role in the development of production. Paint coatings are widely used to protect industrial products, equipment and metal structures where there is an intense impact of aggressive media on structural materials [3]. One of the effective ways to protect parts and apparatus in the chemical and oil-refining industries, chemical engineering, chemical water treatment shops are polymer coatings. The protection of metals and

other structural materials from corrosion is an important task and especially in the chemical industry, where equipment and structures are subject to the greatest corrosion destruction. Unlike other industries, building structures and equipment of chemical enterprises are operated under conditions of constant exposure to liquid, vapor and gaseous, as well as solid aggressive media released at the intermediate and final stages of the technological process. The creation of technological foundations for the chemical processing of waste in order to obtain anti-corrosion polymer coatings for the needs of the Republic of Kazakhstan is an important issue and contributes to the saving of natural raw materials of the Republic. The problem is solved by the development of a fundamentally new, innovative anti-corrosion material which with relative cheapness, has a high chemical resistance. A sufficiently wide application for corrosion protection in the petrochemical, oil and gas and machine-building industries has found such coatings from composite polymeric paint and varnish materials, the main components of which are oligomers. The most common of the modified epoxy resins found compositions - epoxixylitane resins in the modification with gossypol resin. The composition and properties of gossypol resin depend on the quality of the raw materials, compliance with the technological modes of fat decomposition, the depth of distillation of fatty acids and other factors. The problem of increasing the reliability and durability of parts (assemblies) of machines and equipment has acquired particular relevance at the present stage of production development [4]. At the moment, developments aimed at increasing the service life of existing facilities: construction metal structures, oil and gas pipe pipes, technological equipment in machine-building machinery and others are of great importance. One of these ways is the development of composite materials consisting of epoxixylitane resin and waste from the fat-and-oil industry. The chemical composition of gossypol resin is neo-natural. The basis of gossypol resin is free fatty acids, then polymerized fatty acids, as well as gossypol and products of its thermal and chemical conversion due to polycondensation with amino acids, carbohydrates and other components present in cotton seed. The composition and properties of gossypol resin depend on the quality of the raw materials, compliance with technological regimes. For the development of new generations of anti-corrosion coatings with low cost and high efficiency an easily accessible industrial waste was chosen as the main raw material - gossypol resin - oligomer, the quality indicators of which are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Physical and chemical characteristics of gossypol resin

gossypol resin	properties
visual appearance	viscous– fluid mass
colour	from dark brown to black
acid value, mg	50 -100
ash content, weight %	1,0 - 1,25
moisture and volatile substances content, %	up to 46
specific weight, g/cm ³	0,98 - 0,998
saponification number, mg	80 - 130

Anti-corrosion polymer coating developed on the basis of epoxysylitane and gossypol resin, plasticizer, filler and hardener is weighed with an accuracy of 0.01 g. Upon 30-40 minutes, the coating is thoroughly mixed, after which it is suitable for consumption. Curing of the coating takes place at 18-200C within 6-8 hours. In the drying process, the reaction between the mass and the applied surface is completed. The

properties of anti-corrosion coating based on epoxysylitane and gossypol resin are shown in Table 2.

The study of the physical and mechanical properties of the composition of the anti-corrosion polymer coating indicates that the proposed composition of the coating has good physical and mechanical properties and can be used in the oil refining, oil and gas and machine-building industries.

Table 2

Physical and mechanical properties of anti-corrosion coating based on epoxysylitane and gossypol resin

properties	indicators
hardness according to M-3, equivalent unit after drying at a temperature of 0C, not less than 100-110 ⁰ C	0,98
18-20 ⁰ C	0,90
bending of the coating, mm, not more than	1
gel fraction, %	98
plasticity, %	15
comfortability while applying	good
cross-hatch test before testing, score	1
cross-hatch test after testing, score	1
impact strength, kg/cm	50
water absorption per day, %	0,53
duration of preservation of viscoplastic properties on the surface, min	30 – 40
drying time at 18-20 0C, h.	6-8
surface condition after drying	homogeneous, smooth, glan-ce

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